

A survey on smart transportation

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Abstract

This survey analyzes the importance of having an effective system to successfully move from one place to another. In today's world, transportation is closely linked with technological innovation and sustainability. The study highlights how intelligent transportation systems, powered by the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), are transforming urban mobility. These smart systems enhance efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and improve the quality of life in modern cities. The integration of digital technologies into transportation networks is becoming essential for building more sustainable and intelligent infrastructures.

Key words: Internet of things, intelligent transportation, ai, sustainability, autonomous vehicles, smart cities

Introduction

From the beginning of its existence, humans always try to find ways to make their lives easier.

In everyday life, working individuals try to find the best way to reach their work. They use cars, trains, buses and metro. Here is where technology and traditional means of transport meet.

The demand for smarter, greener, and safer transport solutions has led to the emergence of the smart transportation system. This system integrates advanced computing, communication, and sensing technologies into transportation networks. It goes beyond traditional ITS by enabling real-time data collection, vehicle autonomy, and predictive analytics. The synergy between vehicles,

infrastructure, and users has become the cornerstone of modern urban mobility strategies. After this introduction follows the state of art which consists of four chapters and then the conclusion and the references.

State of art

1. From Intelligent transportation system to smart transportation system

Since the 20th century, a time in which most advance technological innovations first appear, there have been a lot of changes in the ways people [1]. As the population grew, ways to make the transportation system more efficient where needed and that's when the intelligent transportation system was created. The ITS combines high technology and improvements in information systems, communication sensor and advancement mathematical methods with the conventional word of surface transportation infrastructure [1]. It is believed that Phelps Eno was the first person do talk about traffic safety and why is it important [2]He was also the first person to make traffic rules such as the pedestrian crosswalk, traffic regulation, taxi stand and pedestrian safety.

In the 1930s in the United States, most people lied on public transportation in order to move from one place to another, since there weren't many freeways and having a personal vehicle sometimes was not an option. That's when the need of ITS was highlighted [3].

In the 1990, the intelligence transportation system was put to the test in the United States. They featured special GPS tracking devices which mainly helped control the traffic. In 1993 the ITS evolved from intelligent transportation system to smart transportation system (STS), after the Internet became public [4]. The smart transportation system uses sensors and data to analyse possible outcomes and possibilities of automation and ride-sharing vehicles by providing more completed solutions, in real time with more flexible flexibility [4]. Recent research highlights how STS supports the deployment of connected and autonomous vehicle services within the broader smart mobility framework of modern cities [5]. It can also use ai, IoT, big data and 5G.

The rapid technological evolution has created several tools that can be used in the smart transport systems. Firstly, the Internet of Things create the ability for two vehicles to connect with each other or to connect users in one united space which collects data in real time [6]. This is very useful for tools like intelligent parking sensors, that allow a better view and understanding of the space that the vehicle takes or needs [7]. Recent work has also examined how IoT can support emergency response, such as IoT-enabled ambulances in smart cities, highlighting its potential to enhance urban mobility and citizen well-being during disasters [8]Additionally artificial intelligence can be used also to process data and the “behaviour” of automated vehicles in order to eliminate accidents and

problems on the road. 5G technology provides better speed in the data analysis process [9]. Lastly big data uses data from GPS devices, phone apps, traffic cameras and even cell phone cameras to give useful information and support decisions in the transportation system [10].

Some countries have already understood the importance of STS so well that they have tried to make several adjustments to the current transportation system and regulations [11]. The European Union and the European Parliament have adopted some instructions about the development and the need for safe data of smart transportation system to all country members [12]. Additionally, the United States have created several programmes with the secretary of transportation, since 2015, in order to promote the use of the intelligent transportation system and the smart transportation system referring to them as smart city challenge or connected city [13].

2. Technological elements of smart transportation system

The evolution of the means used in transport has created new categories of smart vehicles that use Internet of vehicles (IoV) that is also called IoX meaning internet of everything [14] , [15]. The IoV uses wireless technology and the internet to connect with other vehicles [16]. The connection is established by the different types of IoV such as V2V meaning vehicle- to- vehicle connections, V2I meaning vehicle to infrastructure, vehicle to pedestrian (V2P) [17] and V2N, which is vehicle to network [18]. Each category of IoV expresses a different way of communication. For example, vehicle to vehicle communication is all about one vehicle connecting and exchanging information about its speed, direction or driver to another vehicle [14]. Another important category is vehicle to infrastructure which include the communication towards traffic signs [19]. It's used to measure the traffic on the roads and comparing them to older data from the same place some time ago. This form is mostly found in GPS, since the main goal of the device is to direct and find the best way for the driver to go from one place to another. The category vehicle to pedestrian is used to secure citizens and pedestrians safety through sensors while drive cars drive by [20]. Lastly V2N is used to access data from the weather forecast, emergency and traffic data from internet or other networks. All the types mentioned above are the reason why the smart transportation system has become more sensitive to environmental and surrounding changes Is able to perform well in real life situations.

For the systems to work, sensors, cameras and GPS system are needed. Constant traffic monitoring ensures that all safety measures are well respected. Recent studies have concluded that ai can be used to check traffic cameras and behaviors to create and analyze data. Research from 2020 proposed a distributed smart parking system that utilizes Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks for stochastic periodic predictions based on data from parking sensors. This approach enhances real-time traffic monitoring and predictive analysis,

contributing to more efficient traffic management [21]. The smart transportation systems then can use data to detect and prevent difficult situations, accidents, traffic patterns and generally traffic [22]. This combination of tools ensures safe traffic management and efficient distribution of traffic flows.

A smart way to manage traffic is by installing smart traffic lights and adaptive signal control [23]. For example, there can be traffic lights that can show, in real time, how many cars are on the same road. This is done by changing colours, just like the colours that map apps use [24]. There is a new system called ADSTLS (Adaptive and Dynamic Smart Traffic Light System) that aims to manage traffic to make the access to the emergency lane for ambulances and firefighters more efficient [23]. The way ADSTLS works is that it consists of a synchronizing number of traffic lights controlling consecutive junctions by creating a delay between the times at which each of them switches to green in each direction. This delay is dynamically updated based on the number of vehicles waiting at each junction, thereby allowing vehicles leaving the city center to travel a long distance without stopping [25]. This system can also lower the carbon footprint, since it does not “make” a car stay in the same spot for a long time. Similar smart city frameworks that integrate IoT and UAVs have been proposed to optimize emergency logistics and support traffic coordination during disasters, contributing to a more resilient transportation infrastructure [26].

The collection and analysis of the traffic data needs a computer system with a lot of space and a high-power processor, that can handle a huge amount of information, pictures, video and audio to be able to create a usable and real traffic management plan. This is where cloud get used. Cloud computing allows data to be saved and edited, which makes it perfect for historic data analysis, meaning comparing data for the same place in different times or seasons, and to teach AI models how to collect data [27]. This infrastructure has been used in IoT-based traffic systems to support dynamic routing for emergency services and real-time decision-making in crisis situations [28]. Except from cloud computing, edge computing exists. Edge computing can analyse data very close to the problematic situations such as traffic junctions, traffic lights or even self-sufficient vehicles which allow instant decisions to be made that result in low traffic delays [29]. The combination of both systems creates balance between speed and computing power.

For all those helpful systems to work, accurate geographical location is needed. Geographical information systems (GIS) are used analyse and show data such as roads, traffic, traffic junctions, drivers' behaviour, the land usage etc [30]. The information that's collected through the mapping of an area can be useful when it comes to the design of new transport networks, the analysis of impacts (e.g. traffic congestion in high-demand areas) and the optimization of the interconnection of transport modes with the needs of the population [31]. GIS can also be useful in

situations like improving urban management, such as complaint tracking and optimizing waste collection routes [32].

3. Connected and self-sufficient vehicles (CAV)

In the recent years, technology has been part of most aspects of everyday life including transportation, communication and safety. Technology took what used to be a dream or a Hollywood science fiction movie and turned it into a new reality. So naturally Transportation has changed. As already mentioned, we have smart transportation systems and, we have tried to introduce smart technology and traffic management into a safe plan for public.

Since the creation of the first car in 1886, by Carl Benz one of the founders of Mercedes-Benz, a lot has changed [33]. From a “vehicle with a gas engine”, we went to vehicles that run on gas, diesel and electric energy. The new innovative type is connected and self-sufficient vehicles, which can be connected or in a large system as mentioned in the above section. But what are their features. Connected and self-sufficient vehicles promise to make the road safety better by lowering the rate of human mistakes, that are the 1st and the most common cause of accidents [34]. Self-sufficient and connected vehicles can predict the outcome of dangerous situations and avoid them. The needed connections for the predictions to be efficient are V2V and V2I. Some researches have shown that these types of autonomous and self-sufficient vehicles can reduce traffic congestion four times more often than with traditional cars that require driver. Also, they can speed up the traffic flow by 30% in relation with regular cars that are driven by people [35]. CAV can also be proven to be a safer option for both bicycle users and pedestrians [36]. Some studies have shown that installing or teaching human behavior in CAVs can benefit vulnerable groups like pedestrians and small HDS [37]. Additionally, recent research has proposed a Time of Arrival (ToA) estimation system aimed at supporting efficient cycling in smart cities. This system enhances the safety and integration of bicycles within urban smart transportation frameworks by enabling more accurate predictions of cyclists’ movements, ultimately contributing to safer coexistence between CAVs, human-driven vehicles, and vulnerable road users [38].

Since the release of CAVs, there have been some safety problems with their coexistence on the same roads with traditional cars or human driven vehicles (HDV). This is due to differences in reaction times, communication capabilities, and driving behaviors [39]. While CAVs can moderate stop-and-go waves and improve traffic efficiency, their effectiveness depends on penetration rates, and connectivity, which can influence accident risks in mixed traffic environments [40]. Moreover, in case of difficult weather circumstances sensors might not be able to work efficiently leading to accidents [41]. Additional sensors can give false positive or negative signals if it’s snowing. Sometimes snowflakes or heavy rain can be interpreted as objects leading to sudden stops, turns and collisions [42].

In areas where there is a lot of light pollution, cameras that rely on light might not be able to accurately detect the lines on the road [43]. Lastly, rain and snow can attenuate radar signals and create wrong data, reducing detection range and causing interference that masks actual targets [44].

The coexistence of CAV and HDV also raises legal and ethical challenges. The challenge with the most importance is in case of an accident is who is liable [45]. Is it the owner, the manufacturer or the programmer? [46]. Since the CAVs use programs, cameras and sensors it is difficult for the vehicle to have social sensitivity that leads to ethical decisions. Additionally, in case of an accident the CAV can't know whose life should protect or how it needs to react even to the smallest possibility of crashing and AI does not have all the data required to make a good decision based on the information from the sensors and cameras. This creates uncertainty between conflicting outcomes [47]. Another challenge is whether human privacy is not threatened. The continuous data collection and exchange with the vehicle create a constant worry for whoever use it. At the same time, people worry that this exchange will lose their private information and even lead to a system hacking [45].

It is believed that the coexistence of traditional vehicles and CAVs will last more than a hundred years, since they are a quite early innovation. The European union has tried to set some principals in the field of ethics, society, privacy, justice, road safety, economy and responsibility [48]. There need to be some standards, so people do not feel threatened or in danger [47]. Lastly, issues with algorithmic decision-making and social acceptance should be taken into consideration [49].

4. Environmental impact and sustainability

Moving around today's cities is not just a matter of speed and ease; it is also a matter of environmental responsibility. As cities grow and traffic increases, the impact of transport on the environment is becoming increasingly apparent [50]. Smart transport systems come to propose solutions: from routes chosen with the lowest emission of pollutants (eco-routing) in mind, to congestion pricing systems that prevent unnecessary traffic in already congested areas [51].

Smart transportation systems are designed to smooth traffic flow, traffic congestion and to boost the use of sustainable means of transport like public bikes and electrical buses [52]. The need that is being sought is the reduction of the carbon footprint. This is accomplished by optimizing the route buses use, so that the vehicles cover the shortest possible distance [53]. Moreover, as has already been discussed, smart traffic lights can be used with ai to tone down the unnecessary "stop-start" [54]. Also, more electrical chargers can be made. This eases the access to electrical energy, which is electric vehicles "fuel" and shows the will to move on with renewable energy sources. Furthermore, the promotion of ridesharing contributes to the reduction of carload on the road [55]. All these ways lead to less non-renewable fuel used and to lower carbon footprint.

The policies and the strategies that aim to lower traffic congestion, especially in big cities or big cultural centres are urban congestion pricing and eco-routing. Urban congestion pricing refers to the extra charges to vehicles that use the road during peak hours [56]. This aims to discourage the possible unnecessary use of cars and to make citizens use public transport or other environment friendly options [57]. Eco-routing is an advanced method of route selection, which not only aims at the fastest or shortest route but also prioritizes lower fuel consumption and reduction of pollutant emissions. Instead of choosing the route based on traditional criteria (such as distance or time), the system analyses environmental parameters and energy data [50]. For example, a vehicle can avoid a route that has a lot of traffic lights and is on a busy road and opt to find a “quiet” road. Another example is a route which contains steep elevation fluctuations. The system can choose a route with less gradient, which will require less energy for the same vehicle.

The analysis of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a scientific approach for assessing the environmental footprint of a transport system throughout its lifetime [58]. In the field of transportation, LCA make it possible to calculate the negative impact of a vehicle construction, its life, meaning the amount of time that the vehicle is being used, and the end of its usability. The vehicle construction refers also to electric cars, buses and motorbikes. The faze of life consists of the counting of CO₂ emissions and the consumption of fuel and solar energy [59]. Lastly the end of life is all about recycling and disposal of materials and components. Concluding, this analysis creates an easier way to compare different vehicles, like electric vs diesel engine vehicles about their environmental impact [60].

Conclusion

Internet of Things (IoT) is a world-wide network connecting all smart objects together. It enables things to talk to each other. The development of smart transportation systems is a clear response to the increasing demands of modern urban mobility. Technologies such as V2X communication, AI-powered traffic analysis, and eco-routing offer new levels of optimization in public and private transport. At the same time, environmental sustainability and ethical concerns about privacy and safety must be addressed. As smart systems evolve, a balanced approach that incorporates both technological innovation and social responsibility is essential. The future of mobility depends on intelligent, adaptable, and ethically sound transportation frameworks.

References

- [10] A. Mohandu and M. Kubendiran, “Survey on Big Data Techniques in Intelligent Transportation System (ITS),” *Materials Today Proceedings*, vol. 47, pp. 8–17, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.03.479.

[3] Auer, Ashley, et al. "History of Intelligent Transportation Systems". 1 May 2016, rosap.ntl.bts.gov/view/dot/30826.

[6] Atif, Yacine et al. "Internet of Things Approach to Cloud-based Smart Car Parking". *Procedia Computer Science*, volume 98, 2016, Pages 193-198., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.09.031>.

[55] B. Caulfield, "Estimating the environmental benefits of ride-sharing: A case study of Dublin," *Transportation Research Part D Transport and Environment*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 527–531, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2009.07.008.

[24] B. Ghazal, K. ElKhatib, K. Chahine and M. Kherfan, "Smart traffic light control system". *2016 Third International Conference on Electrical, Electronics, Computer Engineering and their Applications (EECEA)*, Beirut, Lebanon, 2016, pp. 140-145, doi: 10.1109/EECEA.2016.7470780.

[22] B. Wang. "Edge Computing and AI-driven Intelligent Traffic Monitoring and Optimization." *www.ewadirect.com*, June 2024, doi:10.54254/2755-2721/77/2024MA0062.

[52] C. Zhao, K. Wang, X. Dong, and K. Dong, "Is smart transportation associated with reduced carbon emissions? The case of China," *Energy Economics*, vol. 105, p. 105715, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105715.

[25] D. Aleko and D. Soufiene. "An Efficient Adaptive Traffic Light Control System for Urban Road Traffic Congestion Reduction in Smart Cities." *Information*, vol. 11, no. 2, Feb. 2020, p. 119, doi:10.3390/info11020119.

[4] Damiola, Oladimeji."Smart transportation: an overview of technologies and applications." *Sensors* 23.8 (2023): 3880.

[48] De Sio, Filippo Santoni. "The European Commission Report on Ethics of Connected and Automated Vehicles and the Future of Ethics of Transportation." *Ethics and Information Technology*, vol. 23, no. 4, Sept. 2021, pp. 713–26, doi:10.1007/s10676-021-09609-8

[12] "Directive - 2010/40 - EN - EUR-LEX." https://eurlex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2010/40/oj/eng?utm_

[39] Dong, Jiakuan, et al. "Impact of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles on Traffic Safety of Mixed Traffic Flow: From the Perspective of Connectivity and Spatial Distribution." *Transportation Safety and Environment*, vol. 4, no. 3, Aug. 2022, doi:10.1093/tse/tdac021.

[56] F. Zong, M. Zeng, and Y.-X. Li, "Congestion pricing for sustainable urban transportation systems considering carbon emissions and travel habits," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 101, p. 105198, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2024.105198.

[57] G. S. Olusanya, M. O. Eze, O. Ebiesuwa, and C. Okunbor, "Smart transportation system for solving urban traffic congestion," *Review of Computer Engineering Studies*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 55–59, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.18280/rces.070302.

[30] Harris, Trevor M., and Gregory A. Elmes. "The Application of GIS in Urban and Regional Planning: A Review of the North American Experience." *Applied Geography*, vol. 13, no. 1, Jan. 1993, pp. 9–27, doi:10.1016/0143-6228(93)90077-e.

[41] Hou, Guangyang. "Evaluating Efficiency and Safety of Mixed Traffic With Connected and Autonomous Vehicles in Adverse Weather." *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 4, Feb. 2023, p. 3138, doi:10.3390/su15043138.

[11] "ITS Directive and Action Plan." *Mobility and Transport*, transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/smart-mobility/road/its-directive-and-action-plan_en.

[20] J. J. Anaya, P. Merdrignac, O. Shagdar, F. Nashashibi and J. E. Naranjo, "Vehicle to pedestrian communications for protection of vulnerable road users," *2014 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium Proceedings*, Dearborn, MI, USA, 2014, pp. 1037-1042, doi: 10.1109/IVS.2014.6856553.

[58] J. T. Harvey *et al.*, "Life cycle assessment for transportation infrastructure policy evaluation and procurement for state and local governments," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 22, p. 6377, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11226377.

[17] Kabil, Ahmad *et al.* "Vehicle to Pedestrian Systems: Survey, Challenges and Recent Trends." *IEEE Journals & Magazine/IEEE Xplore*, 24 November 2022, ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9963973.

[49] Keeling, Geoff. "The Ethics of Automated Vehicles." *ResearchGate*, Apr. 2020, doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.28316.10889.

[19] Khan, Aidil Redza, *et al.* "DSRC Technology in Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) IoT System for Intelligent Transportation System (ITS): A Review." *Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, July 2021, pp. 97–106, doi:10.1007/978-981-33-4597-3_10.

[13] Kilcarr, Sean. "AASHTO Journal - USDOT Issues \$130M Worth of SMART Program Grants." *AASHTO Journal*, 20 Dec. 2024, <https://aashtojournal.transportation.org/usdot-issues-130m-worth-of-smart-program-grants/>.

[5] K. Psaraftis, K. Ntalianis, and N. Mastorakis, "Dynamic Carpool matching for employees: Leveraging telematics and user preferences," *WSEAS TRANSACTIONS ON BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS*, vol. 21, pp. 2717–2735, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.37394/23207.2024.21.222.

[47] Książak, Paweł, and Sylwia Wojtczak. "A Human Being Must Obey the Commands of a Robot! CAVs, Asimov's Second Law and the New Ground-Breaking Ethics." *Communications in computer and information science*, 2022, pp. 380–93, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-20316-9_29.

[27] Liu, Guanxiong et al., "Smart Traffic Monitoring System Using Computer Vision and Edge Computing," in *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 12027-12038, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TITS.2021.3109481

[37] Lu, Hongliang, et al. "Empowering Safer Socially Sensitive Autonomous Vehicles Using Human-plausible Cognitive Encoding." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 122, no. 21, May 2025, doi:10.1073/pnas.2401626122.

[14] Maadi, Saeed, et al. "Real-Time Adaptive Traffic Signal Control in a Connected and Automated Vehicle Environment: Optimisation of Signal Planning With Reinforcement Learning Under Vehicle Speed Guidance." *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 19, Oct. 2022, p. 7501, doi:10.3390/s22197501.

[31] M. B. Sushma, S. Roy, and A. Maji, "Development of intelligent decision system for optimized highway corridor planning: an integrated GIS and heuristic approach.," *EBSCOhost*, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.53136/979122180742411.

[32] Mansurova, Madina, et al. "Adaptive City Traffic Lights as Collective IoT Devices." *Studies in systems, decision and control*, 2023, pp. 697–712, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-22938-1_48.

[45] Mamak, Kamil, and Jadwiga Glanc. "Problems With the Prospective Connected Autonomous Vehicles Regulation: Finding a Fair Balance Versus the Instinct for Self-preservation." *Technology in Society*, vol. 71, Sept. 2022, p. 102127, doi:10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.102127.

[35] Mavromatis, Ioannia et al. "On Urban Traffic Flow Benefits of Connected and Automated Vehicles". *IEEE*, 25-28 May 2020, DOI: 10.1109/VTC2020-Spring48590.2020.9128758.

[59] M.A. Kashem, M. Shamsuddoha, and N. Tasnuba. "Smart Transportation and Carbon Emission from the Perspective of Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, and Blockchain: A Review for Sustainable Future."8 Oct. 2024, doi:10.20944/preprints202410.0328.v

[43] M. Brzozowski and P. Krzysztof. "Problems Related to the Operation of Autonomous Vehicles in Adverse Weather Conditions." *Silniki Spalinowe/Combustion Engines*, July 2023, doi:10.19206/ce-168805.

[60] M. J. Eckelman, "Life cycle assessment in support of sustainable transportation," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 021004, May 2013, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/8/2/021004.

[33] Narla, Siva r. K.. "The Evolution of Connected Vehicle Technology: From Smart Drivers to Smart Cars to... Self-Driving Cars". *ITE JOURNAL*, July 2013, <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=b808c3a8ca2f70d223e0cdf69867fab0a39473fb>.

[2] Norton, Louis Arthur. "William Phelps Eno: New York's Architect of Traffic Safety." *New York History*, vol. 98 no. 2, 2017, p. 244-260. *Project MUSE*, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/nyh.2017.0023>.

[54] O. Rinchi, A. Alsharoa, I. Shatnawi, and A. Arora, "The role of intelligent transportation systems and artificial intelligence in energy efficiency and emission reduction," *arXiv.org*, Jan. 25, 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.14560>

[34] Petridou, Eleni, and Maria Moustaki. "Human Factors in the Causation of Road Traffic Crashes." *European Journal of Epidemiology*, vol. 16, no. 9, Jan. 2000, pp. 819–26, doi:10.1023/a:1007649804201.

[16] P. Jing. "An Adaptive Traffic Signal Control in a Connected Vehicle Environment: A Systematic Review." *Information*, vol. 8, no. 3, Aug. 2017, p. 101, doi:10.3390/info8030101.

[51] R. C. Antúnez and M. W. Levin, "How does Eco-Routing affect total system emissions? City network predictions from user equilibrium models," *arXiv.org*, Jul. 24, 2022. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.13698?utm>

[29] R. Singh, S. Agarwal, M. Calder, and P. Bahl, "Cost-effective Cloud Edge Traffic Engineering with Cascara," *USENIX*, 2021. <https://www.usenix.org/conference/nsdi21/presentation/singh?utm>

[46] S. Ayebo and J. John. "Legal Implications of Autonomous Vehicles: Building a Regulatory Framework." *ResearchGate*, Jan. 2025, www.researchgate.net/publication/388075655_Legal_Implications_of_Autonomous_Vehicles_Building_a_Regulatory_Framework.

[50] S. Djavadian, R. Tu, B. Farooq, and M. Hatzopoulou, "Multi-objective eco-routing for dynamic control of connected & automated vehicles," *Transportation Research Part D Transport and Environment*, vol. 87, p. 102513, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2020.102513.

[1] Sussman, Joseph S. "Perspectives on intelligent transportation systems (ITS)". *Springer Science & Business Media*, 2008.

[7] T. Adewale and J. Paul, "AI, 5G, and IoT: How these technologies are creating the perfect storm for smart systems," *ResearchGate*, Nov. 2024, [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/385855348_AI_5G_and_IoT_How_The_se_Technologies_Are_Creating_the_Perfect_Storm_for_Smart_Systems.

- [21] T. Anagnostopoulos, P. Fedchenkov, N. Tsotsolas, K. Ntalianis, A. Zaslavsky, and I. Salmon, "Distributed modeling of smart parking system using LSTM with stochastic periodic predictions," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 32, no. 14, pp. 10783–10796, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00521-019-04613-y.
- [38] T. Anagnostopoulos, K. Ntalianis, C. Skourlas, I. Sosunova, P. Fedchenkov and A. Zaslavsky. "ToA estimation system for efficient cycling in Smart Cities". *21st Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics*, no. 60, pp 1-4, 2017, Larissa, Greece, doi:10.1145/3139367.3139412.
- [28] T. Anagnostopoulos, K. Ntalianis, C. Skourlas and S.R. Jino Rameson. "IoT-enabled fall verification of elderly and impaired people in smart cities". *Association for Computing Machinery*, 27 Nov. 2018, New York, NY, USA, doi: 10.1145/3291533.3291553.
- [8] T. Anagnostopoulos, K. Ntalianis and N. Tsapatsoulis, "IoT-Enabled Ambulances Assisting Citizens' Well-Being after Earthquake Disasters in Smart Cities," *2019 International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE Green Computing and Communications (GreenCom) and IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (CPSCom) and IEEE Smart Data (SmartData)*, Atlanta, GA, USA, 2019, pp. 922-928, doi: 10.1109/iThings/GreenCom/CPSCom/SmartData.2019.00164.
- [26] T. Anagnostopoulos, F. Komisopoulos, I. Salmon, and K. Ntalianis, "UAV-Enabled Supply Chain architecture for flood recovery in smart cities," in *Lecture notes in networks and systems*, 2022, pp. 483–496. doi: 10.1007/978-981-19-5845-8_34.
- [18] T. Dandala, K. Vallidevi and A.Rajan. "Internet of Vehicles (IoV) for traffic management." *2017 International conference on computer, communication and signal processing (ICCCSP)*. IEEE, 2017.
- [53] T. Litman, "Comprehensive evaluation of energy conservation and emission reduction policies," *Transportation Research Part a Policy and Practice*, vol. 47, pp. 153–166, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.tra.2012.10.022.
- [42] V. Arthi et al. "Object Detection of Autonomous Vehicles under Adverse Weather Conditions". *Conference: 2022 International Conference on Data Science, Agents & Artificial Intelligence (ICDSAAI)*, 2022, Doi:10.1109/ICDSAAI55433.2022.10028795.
- [15] Weerasundara, W. a. G., et al. "An Adaptive and Coordinated Traffic Signal Scheme for Greener Transport 4.0." *Lecture notes in electrical engineering*, 2022, pp. 206–17, doi:10.1007/978-981-19-1677-9_18.
- [44] X. Wang. "Radar Signal Behavior in Maritime Environments: Falling Rain Effects." *Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 1, Dec. 2023, p. 58, doi:10.3390/electronics13010058.

[9] Y. Deng. “Application of Intelligent Transportation System Based on 5G”. *Association for Computing Machinery*, 9781450387774, 2021, New York, NY, USA, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3478472.3478478>.

[40] Y. Lanhang and Y. Toshiyuki. “Evaluating the Impact of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles on Traffic Safety.” *Physica a Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications*, vol. 526, Apr. 2019, p. 121009, doi:10.1016/j.physa.2019.04.245.

[23] Zerroug, Rafik, et al. “Adaptive and Dynamic Smart Traffic Light System for Efficient Management of Regular and Emergency Vehicles at City Intersection.” *IET Smart Cities*, vol. 6, no. 4, Aug. 2024, pp. 387–421, doi:10.1049/smc2.12090.

[36] Zhang, Yunchang and Fricker, Jon D. “Smart Interaction - Pedestrians and vehicles in a CAV environment”. *CCAT and Purdue University*, June 2022, <https://docs.lib.purdue.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1014&context=ccat>.